

Adsorptive capture of ionic and non-ionic pollutants using a versatile hybrid amphiphilic-nanomicaceous

Fernando Aguado ¹, Rosa Martín-Rodríguez ², Carmen Pesquera ³, Rafael Valiente ⁴ and Ana C. Perdigón ^{5,*}

¹CITIMAC Department, University of Cantabria, Avda. de Los Castros, 39005, Santander, Spain. Nanomedicine Group, IDIVAL, Avda. Cardenal Herrera Oria s/n, 39011, Santander, Spain; aguadof@unican.es.

²QUIPRE Department, University of Cantabria, Avda. de Los Castros, 46, 39005, Santander, Spain. Nanomedicine Group, IDIVAL, Avda. Cardenal Herrera Oria s/n, 39011, Santander Spain; rosa.martin@unican.es.

³QUIPRE Department, University of Cantabria, Avda. de Los Castros, 46, 39005, Santander, Spain. Nanomedicine Group, IDIVAL, Avda. Cardenal Herrera Oria s/n, 39011, Santander, Spain; carmen.pesquera@unican.es.

⁴Applied Physics Department, University of Cantabria, Avda. de Los Castros, 48, 39005, Santander, Spain. Nanomedicine Group, IDIVAL, Avda. Cardenal Herrera Oria s/n, 39011, Santander, Spain; rafael.valiente@unican.es.

⁵QUIPRE Department, University of Cantabria, Avda. de Los Castros, 46, 39005, Santander, Spain. Nanomedicine Group, IDIVAL, Avda. Cardenal Herrera Oria s/n, 39011, Santander Spain; perdigonac@unican.es.

*Correspondence: perdigonac@unican.es; Tel.: +34942201592

Abstract: A versatile functional nanomaterial for the removal of ionic and non-ionic pollutants is presented in this work. For that purpose, the high charge mica Na-4-Mica was exchanged with the cationic surfactant $C_{16}\text{-NH}(\text{CH}_3)_2^+$. The intercalation of the tertiary amine in the swellable nano-clay provides the optimal hydrophilic/hydrophobic nature in the bidimensional galleries of the nanomaterial responsible for the dual functionality. The fully organo-mica, made by functionalization with $C_{16}\text{H}_{33}\text{NH}_3^+$ was also synthesized for comparison purposes. Both samples were characterized by X-ray diffraction techniques and transmission electron microscopy. Then, the samples were exposed to a saturated atmosphere of cyclohexylamine for two days and the adsorption capacity was calculated by thermogravimetric measurements. Eu^{3+} cations have served as a proof of concept for the adsorption of ionic pollutants in aqueous solution. Optical measurements have been used to identify the adsorption mechanism of Eu^{3+} cations, since Eu^{3+} emission, including the relative intensity of different transitions as well as the luminescence lifetime, can be used as an ideal spectroscopic probe to characterize the local environment of Eu^{3+} . Finally, the stability of the amphiphilic hybrid nanomaterial after the adsorption has also been tested.

Keywords: high charge mica; adsorption; calorimetry; decontamination

1. Introduction

Organic-inorganic hybrid nanomaterials represent a clever strategy to design new functional materials that combines the optimal level of hydrophobicity created by an organic molecule or polymer, -required for different industrial uses- with the structural properties of an inorganic component, preferentially thermal and mechanical stability [1]. The intercalation of organic species in lamellar solids, specifically in clay platelets, constitutes an important example of organically modified 2D nanocomposites with a great presence in the industrial market [2-4]. In particular, organic nano-clays have been proposed as efficient adsorbents to remove organic pollutants, such volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and other non-ionic hydrocarbons (NOCs), from air and water, because of its numerous advantages, mainly its relative low cost, high surface area and mechanical stability, among others [5,6]. High charge micas is a family of layered aluminosilicates with improved adsorption properties, with a loading capacity up to four times compared with other low charged aluminosilicates, bentonites, and from which a set of organo-clays has been successfully synthesized [7-9]. Also, those functionalized nanomaterials, made by the incorporation of long chain alkylammonium cations in the galleries of the clay, have already demonstrated its capacity to capture different NOCs such phenol, benzene and toluene through an adsorptive removal mechanism [10].

A deep knowledge of the driven forces involved in the intercalation process and in the surface chemistry is crucial to fully control the synthesis processes and to understand the adsorption mechanism. Several factors, such as the electrostatic attraction between the surfactant polar head group and the nano-clay surface, the amount and configuration of the organic species inside the layers, the attractive Van der Waals forces between tails and the level of hydrophobicity/solubility of the surfactant play a fundamental role in the final properties and applicability of the products [11]. In that way, we have recently described an experimental route to synthesize nanostructured organo-micas prepared from primary and tertiary C16 amines. A controlled adsorption of the organics leads to a tunable hydrophobicity in the interlayer space of the hybrid material. This provides the possibility to choose the optimal interface nature, as it is required for a variety of applications, from a fully hydrophobic medium to an amphiphilic quasi-solution [12]. Specifically, an organo-mica with an homogeneous single phase organic-clay is formed upon exchange reaction with long primary n-alkylammonium cations. On the contrary, a synthesis route in which the exchange capacity of the high charge mica is not fully satisfied has been proposed for a more amphiphilic interface by the incorporation of long tertiary amines. For the adequate synthesis of the first type of functionalized mica, the organo-mica, the length of the surfactant is a crucial parameter to assure a quantitative uptake of the surfactant by the attractive Van der Waals interactions

between the alkyl chains. However, the head group of the surfactant, in terms of size -steric effects-, and nature – hydrophobicity-, is the fundamental parameter that controls the final product of the second-one, the amphiphilic-mica. In the latter case, a hydrated homogeneous mixed inorganic-organic interlayer is synthesized. This hybrid material allows to combine exchangeable inorganic cations and adsorbent organic species between the solid layers, constituting a promising adsorbent material with dual functionality, of both hydrophilic and hydrophobic pollutants for water and air decontamination. Besides, the surfactant molecules are able to swell the interlayer space of the aluminosilicate taking the layers apart, thus making the Lewis acidic centers accessible to contaminants in a complementary adsorption mechanism. Despite the promising features exhibited by this functionalized material, its affinity for inorganic and organic species has not been analyzed in detail before.

We present in this work a deep insight into the dual functionality of the amphiphilic-mica as a versatile adsorbent for ionic and non-ionic pollutants. For that purpose, the swellable high charge mica Na-4-Mica was exchanged with the tertiary $(R-NH(CH_3)_2)^+$ amine with alkyl length $R = 16$. The organo-mica, $C_{16}H_{33}NH_3^+$ -mica, was also synthesized, by cation exchange reaction. This organo-mica has been previously reported as an improved adsorbent material of hydrophobic VOCs for water decontamination [10]. Then, both functionalized clays were firstly exposed to a saturated atmosphere with cyclohexylamine. Cyclohexylamine is a strong organic base that is used widely as a corrosion inhibitor and it is toxic at high exposure levels [13]. Under this non-favored condition, a comparative analysis of their adsorption capacities for non-ionic compounds was carried out. In a second step, the sample $C_{16}H_{33}NH(CH_3)_2^+$ -mica was put in contact with a Eu^{3+} water solution as a proof of concept of its capacity to adsorb inorganic contaminant cations. Eu^{3+} cations incorporated in the interlayer space of high charge mica has been recently proposed as an ideal luminescent probe to determine the sorption behavior and cation environment [14]. The functionalized high charge micas were firstly characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The physisorbed cyclohexylamine was analyzed by thermogravimetric (TG) and mass spectroscopy analysis. The interlayer exchange of Na^+ by Eu^{3+} in the amphiphilic-mica has been monitored by luminescence measurements since the Eu^{3+} sharp-line emission, including the relative intensity of different transitions as well as the luminescence lifetime can be used as an ideal spectroscopic probe to characterize the local environment of Eu^{3+} . For that purpose, a doped Eu^{3+} Mica-4 was also synthesized and characterized by XRD, TG and optical measurements.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Synthesis of high charge micas

Na-4-Mica, with four negative charges per unit cell in its structure and ideal chemical formulae $\text{Na}_4[\text{Mg}_6\text{Si}_4\text{Al}_4\text{O}_{20}\text{F}_4]\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$, has been synthesized following the “NaCl method” described by Park et al. Stoichiometric amounts of SiO_2 , (from Sigma, purity 99.8 %), $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ (from Riedel-de-Haën, purity 99.7 %), MgF_2 (from Aldrich, purity 99.9 %), and twofold the stoichiometric amount of NaCl (from Panreac, purity 99.9 %) were well mixed in an agate mortar. Reactants were thermally treated in a Pt crucible at 900 °C for 15 h and leave to cool down. After cooling, the solid was washed with deionized water to eliminate the excess of NaCl and dried at room temperature.

2.2. Synthesis of the organo and the amphiphilic-mica

The chemical products used for the preparation of the organo-mica and the amphiphilic-mica, hexadecylamine (RNH_2) and dimethylhexadecylamine [$\text{RNH}_2(\text{CH}_3)_2$] with $R = 16$, respectively, were obtained from Aldrich Chemical Co. Neutral amines, were firstly converted to the protonated form by adding them in a HCl aqueous solution 0,1 M, in a molar ratio amine:HCl 1:1 and stirred at 80 °C for 3h. Then, 1 g of Na-4-Mica was added to the protonated amines and left to react up to 24h at 80 °C. An amount of two-fold excess the clay CEC of the amines was used in order to favour the cation exchange reaction. Both the organo-clay and the amphiphilic clay were recovered by centrifugation, washed with deionized water and ethanol and dried at room temperature.

2.3. Adsorption of cyclohexylamine and Eu^{3+} cations

The organo-mica and the amphiphilic-mica were put in contact with a saturated atmosphere of cyclohexylamine for 48 h hours. For the adsorption of Eu^{3+} 300 mg of Mica-4, organo-mica and amphiphilic samples were dispersed in 50 mL of a $\text{Eu}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ (REacton 99.9 %) water solution 0.01 M, respectively. The process was repeated three more times. Then, the samples were centrifuged and washed with deionized water.

2.4. Characterization

XRD patterns were obtained with a Bruker D8 Advance instrument using $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation at 40 kV and 30 mA. Diffractograms were obtained from 1.5° to 70° (2θ) at a scanning speed of 0.05 deg.min⁻¹ and a counting time of 5 s.

TG analysis was performed on a Setaram Setsys evolution TGA-DTA/DSC model. The sample was heated from room temperature to 800 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ in air. Approximately 20 mg of sample was heated in an open platinum crucible.

TEM images were obtained on a JEOL JEM 2100 microscope with a CeB₆ filament. TEM samples were prepared by sonication of the powder in ethanol and evaporating one drop onto a holey carbon film.

Steady state luminescence, excitation and lifetime measurements experiments were performed using a FLS920 spectrofluorometer (Edinburgh Instruments) equipped with double-monochromators, a continuous Xe-lamp of 450 W and a pulsed Xe-lamp of 60W(mF920) for excitation and a Hamamatsu R928 photomultiplier tube (PMT) for detection. All emission spectra were corrected for the system response.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Functionalization of Na-4-Mica

Figure 1 includes the diffraction analysis and TEM images of the starting samples, the organo-mica, C₁₆H₃₃NH₃⁺-mica and the amphiphilic-mica, C₁₆H₃₃NH(CH₃)₂⁺-mica, respectively. The XRD diagram of the organo-mica shows a principal reflection attributed to the (001) basal reflection with an associated d spacing value of 4.4 nm. The high interlayer space has been previously associated to a paraffin bilayer structure of the surfactant with double all-trans conformation, with the hydrophobic tails pointing toward the interlayer space tilted 58.2 ° away from the clay surface [7,11]. The existence of other (001) reflections in the diffraction pattern and the regularly ordered layered structure that can be observed from the TEM image in the figure, confirm the homogeneous distribution and densely packaging of the surfactant in the galleries of the clay. As a consequence, a hydrophobic/hydrophilic hybrid material made of alternating hydrophobic galleries fully occupied by surfactant cations and hydrophilic clay layers, is generated for the fully displacement of the interlayer sodium cations by the organic species.

In addition, due to the attractive interaction between the organic tails, a quantitative uptake of the surfactant and even an additional adsorption has been described for surfactants with long alkyl chains, since the Van der Waals forces are proportional to the number of CH₂ groups (1-1,5 kJ per CH₂ group) [15]. For the other sample, the amphiphilic-mica, the XRD diagram exhibits a (001) reflection situated at 2.7° 2θ with a basal space of 3.3 nm, compatible with a paraffin bilayer arrangement of the dimethylhexadecylammonium surfactant on the galleries of the silicate, with a tilting angle of 32.2°. The resulting tilting angle of 32.2° and the displacement of the (001) reflection up to 3.3 nm suggest a partial

replacement of the hydrated sodium cations by the organics as it has been confirmed by TG measurements. Additionally, the formation of a heterostructure or a segregation arrangement can be discarded evidenced by the absence of a second basal reflection family corresponding to hydrated sodium in the interlayer [16].

Figure 1. XRD patterns of the amiphilic-mica, $C_{16}H_{33}NH(CH_3)_2^+-mica$ (a) and the organo-mica, $C_{16}H_{33}NH_3^+-mica$ (c); and TEM images of the amiphilic-mica (b) and the organic-mica (d).

3.2. Adsorption of cyclohexylamine

Firstly, cyclohexylamine has been used as the model for organic contaminant and its uptake by the adsorbent materials has been calculated using TG measurements. Figure 2 includes the TG-DSC curves of the hybrid materials before and after the adsorption of cyclohexylamine.

Figure 2. TG (solid line) and DSC (dashed line) plots for $C_{16}H_{33}NH_3^+$ -mica (a), $C_{16}H_{33}NH(CH_2)_2^+$ -mica (b) and the samples after cyclohexylamine adsorption (c) and (d), respectively

Three different regions can be identified in the mass loss curve of the organic functionalized micas [17-19]. Up to 170 °C a first mass loss step, associated with an endothermic peak in the heat flow curve, is related to desorption of water from the clay mineral and dehydration of the interlayer cation. For the pure organo-mica there is not mass loss in that region according to the structure introduced above. However, the mass loss in the amphiphilic-mica curve is about 2.2 % corroborating the presence of inorganic cations in the interlayer space. In the second region, between 170 °C and 500°C, the mass loss is associated with the thermal oxidation of the organics in the interlayer space of the clay and it is also accompanied with one or more exothermic peaks in the heat flow curve. The combustion process could be prolonged to higher temperatures depending on the nature of the organic matter, the amount of the adsorbed surfactant and oxygen availability.

While the potential use of the organo-mica as an effective absorbent of non-ionic pollutants has been previously probed in aqueous solution, the adsorption capacity for non-ionic contaminants in air has not been tested before. Here, the efficiency of both samples for the cyclohexylamine uptake after being exposed to a saturated atmosphere for two days has been comparatively studied, and the adsorbed amount of cyclohexylamine has been calculated by TG measurements.

The amount of the adsorbed cyclohexylamine has been attributed to the extra-mass loss in the second region of the thermogram. Under these unfavorable conditions compared with an aqueous medium, TG measurements show that cyclohexylamine is not adsorbed in the organo-mica, probably due to the high amount of surfactant molecules closely packed in the interlayer space. In this sample, the surfactant is adsorbed in higher amounts than its cation exchange capacity, so the extra organic molecules could be in the organo-layer saturating the adsorption centers. On the contrary, cyclohexylamine is adsorbed in the amphiphilic sample. The amount of the adsorbed cyclohexylamine has been calculated to be 16 % of the sample mass.

Figure 3. TG (solid line), MS H₂O curve (dots) and MS CO₂ curve (dashed line) $C_{16}H_{33}NH_3^+$ -mica (a), $C_{16}H_{33}NH(CH_3)_2^+$ -mica (b) and the samples after cyclohexylamine adsorption (c) and (d), respectively.

TG experiments of the initial Mica-4 exchanged with $C_{16}H_{33}NH(CH_3)_2^+$ ions shown a ratio of replacement of the 50 % of the interlayer Na^+ (~38 % mass loss). The hybrid material is then organized in a regularly intercalated layered phase, with surfactant cations and sodium cations in an associative distribution, forming hydrophobic and hydrophilic independent clusters in the interlayer space of the aluminosilicate [11]. The composition of the interlayer agrees with

the results extrapolated from the TEM image and the DRX diagram included in figure 1. In the amphiphilic-mica, a homogenous distribution of the organic and inorganic clusters along the interlayer provides the sample with the adequate level of hydrophobicity to facilitate the incorporation of cyclohexylamine in the functionalized material. Also, chemical adsorption of the primary amine onto the Lewis acidic centers, exposed on the silicate surface, can help in the adsorption process. Under this premise, TG measurements show preliminary satisfactory results for the adsorption of non-ionic or hydrophobic VOCs using cyclohexylamine as a tester molecule.

TG-DSC measurements were also monitored by acquiring the CO₂ and H₂O signals of the evolved gas from the thermal treatment using mass spectrometry. Results are included in figure 3. Below 170 °C, the mass loss observed in the thermogram of the amphiphilic-mica, associated to the dehydration process of the inorganic interlayer cations is confirmed by a maximum in the water signal at 100 °C. However, this maximum is absent for the organic-sample in the water signal. As result of the combustion of the organic matter in an air atmosphere at temperatures below 450 °C, the mass loss process in all the samples is accompanied by a maximum in both, the water and the CO₂ signals. This process is prolonged up to a third region where the residual charcoal is fully oxidized above 500 °C, evidenced by a maximum in the CO₂ curve [20]. Thus, mixed ion clays, combining both potentially exchangeable adsorbent organics species and inorganic cations, represents a significant new addition for use as decontaminants of both non-ionic or hydrophobic VOCs and cationic inorganic ions such heavy metals..

3.3. Adsorption of Eu³⁺ cations

Once the retain capacity of cyclohexylamine has been demonstrated in the amphiphilic sample, the adsorption of inorganic contaminants is analyzed in this section using Eu³⁺ as a cationic model. The optical properties of the amphiphilic clay upon contact with a solution of europium nitrate have been studied in detail. Excitation and luminescence measurements of Eu³⁺ has been previously used as a probe to explore the adsorption mechanism of cationic species in high charge micas [21].

Firstly, the structural and optical properties of a doped Eu³⁺ Mica-4 were analyzed for comparative purposes and they presented below. Importantly, the structure of high charge micas presents some particular advantages to be used as

Figure 4. XRD pattern of Na-Mica-4 and Eu³⁺ doped Mica-4 (a) and schematic representation of Mica-4 with Na⁺ cations and Eu³⁺ cations in the interlayer space, respectively (b). TG (solid line), MS H₂O curve (green) of Na⁺-Mica-4 (c) and Eu³⁺-Mica-4 (d).

luminescent sensor to explore the adsorption mechanism of inorganic cations. (1) Absence of undesirable impurities such iron in the structure that can cause luminescence quenching. (2) High charge micas are fluorinated clays with poorly hydrated cations in the interlayer space, it is well known that hydroxyl groups cause luminescence deactivation through nonradioactive processes. (3) Interlayer cations are homogenously distributed along the surface of the aluminosilicate preventing aggregation of lanthanide ions.

Figure 4 includes the XRD pattern of a Eu^{3+} doped Mica-4 sample and a schematic representation of the unit cell with sodium and europium cations in the interlayer space, respectively. The diagram exhibits two (001) basal reflections, the most intense situated at $2\theta \sim 6.3^\circ$ and a shoulder at $2\theta \sim 7.4^\circ$. Since the basal reflection situated at 6.3° 2θ (basal distance = 1.4 nm) is associated with hydrated trivalent cations as inner sphere complex located in the ditrigonal holes of the aluminosilicate, the basal reflection at 7.4° (distance = 1.2 nm) is attributed to hydrated Na^+ cations in the interlayer space of the mica type clay. Attending to the relative intensities of the peaks, an almost complete interlayer cation exchange of Eu^{3+} by Na^+ can be deduced from the XRD diagram, where a predominant of Eu^{3+} exchanged Mica-4 coexists with a minority Na^+ exchanged Mica-4. Figure 4 also shows the TG analysis of Mica-4 before (c) and after (d) the exchange of interlayer Na^+ by Eu^{3+} . The TG measurements were also followed by the water vapor evolution signal with temperature through mass spectrometry (in green). The mass loss curve of swelling phyllosilicates is characterized by one mass loss step below 250°C corresponding to desorption of water from the clay surface and dehydration of interlayer cation. Mica-4 has a mass loss step of ca. 6 % associated to a maximum in the water vapor curve at 86°C .

Figure 5. Excitation spectrum of Eu^{3+} doped Mica-4 recording Eu^{3+} at 610 nm (a) and emission spectrum of Eu^{3+} doped Mica-4 upon excitation at 394 nm (b). The inset show the time dependence of the Eu^{3+} emission intensity in logarithmic scale.

The number of water molecules in the coordination sphere for each Na^+ cations has been calculated to be 0.7 from the 6 % water loss, in agreement with previous reports. The sample exchanged with Eu^{3+} cations shows more than one mass loss step below 250°C suggesting the existence of water molecules with different strength attached to the silicate.

The associated water vapor curve presents two maxima at ~ 130 °C and ~ 180 °C, respectively. The mass loss step of the Eu^{3+} exchanged Mica-4 is ~ 9 %, which corresponds to 3.8 water molecules per cation. It has to be mentioned that the whole amount of water has been considered to calculate the coordination sphere of Eu^{3+} in the aluminosilicate from TG measurements. In both samples, the interlayer cation adopts an inner-sphere conformation since the number of the existing water molecules are not enough to fully address the coordination sphere of the interlayer cation. Thus the coordination sphere would be completed with the basal oxygens of the tetrahedral sheet.

Sharp-line Eu^{3+} luminescence has been successfully used to study the adsorption mechanism of inorganic cations in different crystalline materials [22-24]. However, the emission bands from Eu^{3+} adsorbed on other silicates are broad and not well resolved, getting limited information about the close environment of the luminescent cation in the host material. Most recently, the optical properties of Eu^{3+} in contact with a high charge mica have been presented as an ideal tool to monitor the cation environment within the clay [14]. Figure 5 includes the excitation (a) and luminescence (b) spectra of Eu^{3+} incorporated in the interlayer of a Mica-4 sample. The excitation spectrum, recorded detecting emission at 610 nm, consists in a set of narrow peaks associated to $f-f$ Eu^{3+} transitions from the ${}^7\text{F}_0$ ground state to the different excited states marked in the figure. The emission spectrum of Eu^{3+} doped Mica-4 was recorded upon excitation at 394 nm. Only the luminescence from the ${}^5\text{D}_0$ Eu^{3+} excited state is usually observed in clay minerals, however, the emission spectrum of the Eu^{3+} doped Mica-4 is composed by sharp-line emission bands from both the ${}^5\text{D}_1$ and ${}^5\text{D}_0$ excited states to the ${}^7\text{F}_J$ ($J=0-4$) low-lying multiplets. The presence of the green Eu^{3+} emission from the ${}^5\text{D}_1$ excited state is associated to Eu^{3+} cations in the interlayer space of the aluminosilicate, in agreement with the XRD results. The inset in Figure 6 shows

Figure 6. Excitation spectrum of Eu^{3+} adsorbed on $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{33}\text{NH}(\text{CH}_3)_2^+$ -mica (a) and emission spectrum of Eu^{3+} adsorbed on $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{33}\text{NH}(\text{CH}_3)_2^+$ -mica (b). The inset show the time dependence of the Eu^{3+} emission intensity in logarithmic scale.

the temporal evolution of the 5D_0 Eu^{3+} emission in logarithmic scale. Clearly, a non-single exponential behaviour is observed. As stated before, the ${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_J$ ($J = 0, 3$) transitions are highly sensitive to the local environment of the Eu^{3+} [23]. Thus, the analysis of the Eu^{3+} optical properties, namely luminescence intensity and lifetime, provides valuable information regarding the adsorption process of the inorganic cations

Figure 6 shows the excitation and emission spectra of Eu^{3+} incorporated in the amphiphilic mica. The observed peaks are assigned to the same transitions as in Fig. 5. The temporal evolution of Eu^{3+} luminescence is also presented in the inset of Fig. 6. Clearly, the decay curve is identical to the one observed for Eu^{3+} in the interlayer of Mica-4. This represents a first evidence of the Eu^{3+} incorporation in the interlayer of the amphiphilic sample. Although its intensity is low (note the scale factor), the observation of the green Eu^{3+} emission from the 5D_1 level is also consistent with the cation incorporation in the amphiphilic mica interlayer. The ${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_0$ transition is very sensitive to the environment, thus, the fact that it is slightly blue-shifted, narrower and more intense in the amphiphilic mica, compared to the Mica-4 sample, is the result of small differences in Eu^{3+} -ligand angles and distances. The intensity ratio of the ${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_2$ and ${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_1$ transitions, R , is usually used as an indication of the Eu^{3+} site asymmetry. The fact that R is two-fold larger in the amphiphilic-mica than in the high-charge mica evidences stronger distortion of the Eu^{3+} coordination complex in the former.

Figure 7. TG (solid line) and DSC (dashed line) plots for on $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{33}\text{NH}(\text{CH}_3)_2^+$ -mica after Eu^{3+} cation adsorption.

Finally, to assure the stability of the functionalized Mica-4 after the Eu^{3+} cations adsorption, the sample was analyzed through TG technique. Figure 7 includes the mass loss curve and DSC analysis from room temperature up to 800 °C.

The mass loss in the first step -below 170 °C- attributed to the loss of water molecules adsorbed in the solid and preferentially from the hydration shell of the interlayer cations, is ~ 3.4 %. The mass loss

is accompanied by an endothermic peak in the DSC curve. This value is a bit superior to its equivalent step observed in the amphiphilic sample $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{33}\text{NH}(\text{CH}_3)_2^+$ -mica.

The increment of the amount of water observed in this region can be explained by the incorporation of Eu^{3+} in the solid as it has been suggested by luminescent measurements.

As it has been introduced before, the mass loss in the second region, between 170 °C and 500°C, is result of the combustion process of the organics in the interlayer space of the clay under an oxidative atmosphere and it is also accompanied with one or more exothermic peaks in the heat flow curve. The mass loss in this second region, after the adsorption of the Eu^{3+} cations, is still the 35 % of the sample mass, similar to the 38 % described for the starting functionalized mica. This fact probes the stability of the sample when it is dispersed in an aqueous media and it is indicative of the ability of the amphiphilic mica to be used as adsorbent for inorganic cations. This adsorption probably occurs in the interlayer space of the sample through a cation exchange mechanism by substituting hydrated sodium cations by Eu^{3+} . However, the clusters of surfactant molecules situated in the bidimensional galleries of the aluminosilicate remain unchanged.

Conclusions

We present in this paper a versatile hybrid material as adsorbent of both ionic and non-ionic pollutants. This dual functionality comes from a combined hydrophobic/hydrophilic interlayer after the functionalization of the high charge mica, Na-4-Mica, with the tertiary $(\text{R-NH}(\text{CH}_3)_2)^+$ amine, being the alkyl length $\text{R} = 16$. The ability of the material to absorb non-ionic compounds has been tested using cyclohexylamine, a strong base, which is toxic at high exposure levels. From TG measurements, an adsorption capacity of 0.2 g of cyclohexylamine per g of hybrid material has been calculated for the amphiphilic mica, under a saturated atmosphere of cyclohexylamine. Under these experimental conditions, this hybrid material has demonstrated a better adsorption ability compared with its homologue, the organo-mica. The amphiphilic sample was then exposed to a Eu^{3+} aqueous solution as a proof of concept of the ability of the adsorbent to incorporate harmful inorganic cations in its structure. Complementarily to XRD, optical measurements of

Eu³⁺ have served as a local probe to identify the adsorption mechanism of Eu³⁺ cations. Specifically, upon comparison with the optical properties of Eu³⁺ in the interlayer of Mica-4, both the ⁵D₀ Eu³⁺ lifetime and the presence of green ⁵D₁ emission corroborates the presence of Eu³⁺ in the amphiphilic clay interlayer. Finally, the stability of the hybrid material is maintained through and after the adsorption process.

Author Contributions: The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Funding: We would like to thank IDIVAL for financial support, Project N° INIVAL19/18.

Acknowledgments: We would like to thank SERMET from University of Cantabria for providing access to the microscope facility.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest. The funders had no role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript, or in the decision to publish the results.

References

1. Sanchez, C.; Julián, B.; Belleville, P.; Popall, M. Applications of hybrid organic-inorganic nanocomposites. *J. Mater. Chem.* **2005**, *15*, 3559-3592. <https://doi.org/10.1039/B509097K>.
2. Ray, S.S.; Okamoto, M. Polymer/layered silicate nanocomposites: a review from preparation to processing. *Prog. Polym. Sci.* **2003**, *28*, 1539-1641. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2003.08.002>.
3. Sinha Ray, S.; Yamada, K.; Okamoto, M.; Ueda, K. New polylactide/layered silicate nanocomposite: a novel biodegradable material. *Nano Lett.* **2002**, *2*, 1093-1096. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ma011613e>.
4. Gilman, J.W.; Jackson, C.L.; Morgan, A.B.; Harris, R.Jr.; Manias, E.; Giannelis, E.P.; Wuthenow, M.; Hilton, D.; Phillips, S.H. Flammability properties of polymer-layered silicate nanocomposites. Propylene and polystyrene nanocomposites. *Chem. Mater.* **2000**, *12*, 1866-1873. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cm0001760>.
5. Xi, Y.; Frost, R.L.; He, H.; Klopogge, T.; Bostrom, T. Modification of Wyoming Montmorillonite surface using a cationic surfactant. *Langmuir* **2005**, *21*, 8675-8680. <https://doi.org/10.1021/la051454i>.

6. Lagaly, G. Interaction of alkylamines with different types of layered compounds. *Solid State Ionics* **1986**, *22*, 43-51. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-2738\(86\)90057-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-2738(86)90057-3).
7. Alba, M.D.; Castro, M.A.; Orta, M.M.; Pavón, E.; Pazos, M.C.; Valencia Rios, J.S. Formation of organo-highly charged mica. *Langmuir* **2011**, *27*, 9711-9718. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/la200942u>.
8. Pazos, M.C.; Castro, M.A.; Orta, M.M.; Pavón, E.; Valencia-Rios, J.S.; Alba, M.D. Synthetic high-charge organomica: Effect of the layer charge and alkyl chain length on the structure of the adsorbed surfactants. *Langmuir* **2012**, *28*, 7325-7332. <https://doi.org/10.1021/la300153e>.
9. Pazos, M.C.; Cota, A.; Osuna, F.J.; Pavón, E.; Alba, M.D. Self-assembling of tetradecylammonium chain on swelling high charge micas (Na-Mica-3 and Na-Mica-2): Effect of alkylammonium concentration and mica layer charge. *Langmuir* **2015**, *31*, 4394-4401. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.langmuir.5b00224>.
10. Pazos, M.C.; Castro, M.A.; Cota, A.; Osuna, F.J.; Pavón, E.; Alba, M.D. New insights into Surface-functionalized swelling high charged micas: Their adsorption performance for non-ionic organic pollutants. *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.* **2017**, *52*, 179-186. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jiec.2017.03.042>.
11. Ijdo, W.L.; Pinnavaia, T.J. Staging of organic and inorganic gallery cations in layered silicate heterostructures. *J. Solid State Chem.* **1998**, *139*, 281-289. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jssc.1998.7842>.
12. Pesquera, C.; Aguado, F.; González, F.; Blanco, C.; Rodríguez, L.; Perdigón, A.C. Tunable interlayer hydrophobicity in a nanostructured high charge organo-mica. *Micro. Meso. Mater.* **2018**, *263*, 77-85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2017.12.006>.
13. Groenewold, G.S.; Ingram, J.C.; Gianotto, A.K.; Appelhans, A.D.; Delmore, J.E. Static secondary ionization mass spectrometry detection of cyclohexylamine on solid surfaces exposed to laboratory air. *J. Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom.* **1996**, *7*, 168-172. [https://doi.org/10.1016/1044-0305\(95\)00638-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/1044-0305(95)00638-9).
14. Martín-Rodríguez, R.; Valiente, R.; Aguado, F.; Perdigón, A.C. Highly efficient photoluminescence from isolated Eu^{3+} ions embedded in high-charge mica. *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2017**, *5*, 10360-10368. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7TC01818E>
15. Streitwieser, A.; Heathcock, C.H.; Kosower, E.M. *Introduction to Organic Chemistry*, 4th ed.; Macmillan: New York, United State, 1992; pp. 75.

16. Pesquera, C.; Aguado, F.; González, F.; Blanco, C.; Rodríguez, L.; Perdígón, A.C. Tunable interlayer hydrophobicity in a nanostructured high charge organo-mica. *Micr. Mesop. Mater.* **2018**, *263*, 77-85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2017.12.006>.
17. Yariv, S.; Borisover, M. Few introducing comments on the thermal analysis of organoclays. *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.* **2011**, *105*, 897-906. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-010-1221-y>.
18. Dweck, J.; Barreto, E.P. Partially exchanged organophilic bentonites. *J. Ther. Anal. Calorim.* **2011**, *105*, 907-913. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-010-1254-2>.
19. Ganguly, S.; Dana, K.; Ghatak, S. Thermogravimetric study of n-alkylammonium-intercalated montmorillonites of different cation exchange capacity. *J. Ther. Anal. Calorim.* **2010**, *100*, 71-78. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-009-0588-0>.
20. Önal, M.; Sarkaya, Y. Thermal analysis of some organoclays. *J. Ther. Anal. Calorim.* **2008**, *91*, 261-265. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10973-007-8319-X>.
21. Martín-Rodríguez, R.; Aguado, F.; Alba, M.D.; Valiente, R.; Perdígón, A.C. Eu³⁺ luminescence in high charge mica: An in situ probe for the encapsulation of radioactive waste in geological repositories. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2019**, *11*, 7559-7565.
22. Baker, M.D.; Ozin, G.A.; Olken, M.M. Laser-induced fluorescence, far-infrared spectroscopy, and luminescence quenching of europium zeolite Y: site-selective probes of extraframework cations. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1988**, *110*, 5709-5714. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja00225a022>.
23. Binnemans, K. Interpretation of europium (III) spectra. *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2015**, *295*, 1-45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccr.2015.02.015>.
24. Guo, H.; Huang, X.; Zeng, Y. Synthesis and photoluminescence properties of novel highly thermal-stable red-emitting Na₃Sc₂(PO₄)₃:Eu³⁺ phosphors for UV-excited white-light-emitting diodes. *J. Alloys Compd.* **2018**, *741*, 300-306.